

TENSILE PROPERTY OF RECYCLED CARBON FIBER STRAND FOR REINFORCEMENT OF CONCRETE

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber (CF) is one of the attractive materials having high strength, light weight, high durability, and CF has been adapted in the field of automobile, aircraft. It means that CF will be discharged as waste in the near future. In this study, the tensile strength of recycle carbon fiber (ReCF) strand, which was made by connecting of discretized ReCF elements, was investigated. In addition, the tensile specimens with epoxy resin impregnation were also tested. It was clarified that the tensile strength of connected specimen was not enough for usage of reinforcement. Impregnation of epoxy resin can, however, improve tensile strength of ReCF strand.

KEYWORDS: sustainability, recycled carbon fiber, braided strands, tensile strength.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic (CFRP), which has an advantage of its higher mechanical properties, is actively used in aircraft and automobiles industries as a substitute for ordinary materials such as iron and aluminum. For example, according to Anaële's research, the wind power sector will have generated CFRP waste of approximately 480,000 tons at the world scale in 2050 (Lefevre, et al., 2019).

Currently, there are various techniques for extracting Recycled Carbon Fibers (ReCF) from CFRP, such as pyrolysis, solvolysis (dissolution treatment with chemicals), and electrolytic oxidation (Kamo, et al., 2018). An example of heating method to extracted ReCF is shown in the Fig. 2. This technology involves heating of CFRP twice. In the first heating, most of the resin in the CFRP is gasification and removed. In the second heating, the material is heated again to burns off all remaining resin. Note that, the thermal energy from the first heating was reused in the second heating. It is possible to extract ReCF with a strength of approximately 90% or more compared to virgin CF (Kumabe, et al., 2022, Moritomi, et al., 2017). Because their length is insufficient for use as reinforcement for concrete structures, development of continuous fiber reinforcement using connected recycled carbon fibers is necessary.

Figure 1: Heating method for recycle carbon fiber

In civil engineering field, it was tried to apply CFRP having higher strength and corrosion resistance to concrete structures as a longitudinal reinforcement. They are not, however, widespread due to economic considerations (Olofin, et al., 2015). Recently, Textile Reinforced Concrete (TRC), which uses CFRP textile as shown in Fig. 1, has been developed and many researches and developments were conducted towards practical application (Muoi. 2020, Zhang, et al., 2019, Peled, et al., 2017, Hegger et al., 2019). In particular, one of the advantages of using lightweight and flexible reinforcement materials can provide good workability during construction.

Figure 2: Carbon textile for TRC

Regarding utilization of ReCF cut into short fibers, there was a trial to make Fiber Reinforced Concrete (FRC). Although the mechanical property of ReCF can enhanced the mechanical properties of FRC. However, it has been reported that mixing of concrete with short ReCF fibers reduced workability. ReCF may also accelerate the corrosion of rebar inside the concrete by forming an electrically continuous circuit and decreasing of resistivity significantly (Kunieda, et al., 2018). Additionally, short CF can generate dust during concrete manufacturing or construction (Masahiro, et al., 2013). Therefore it is difficult to use short ReCF fibers in civil engineering. If long fibers can be produced from ReCF for future, it would be possible to provide an inexpensive continuous fiber reinforcement from the waste, which can also provide durable concrete structures.

This study introduces a process technology to make a continuous strand from discretized ReCF, and tensile strength test of the ReCF strand is conducted. The study uses ReCF having the length of 500mm with and without joint. In addition, the impregnation by epoxy resin was adopted to improve the tensile strength of ReCF strand.

2 TENSILE TEST

2.1 Specimens

As shown in Fig. 3, ReCF elements (approximately 500mm in length) extracted by heating method were prepared. The either end of two elements was then overlapped and spliced together using compressed air to make a joint. To improve the strength of strand itself, the ReCF strands braided, as shown in Fig. 4. The braided ReCF strands having length of more than 30m were wound onto a bobbin as shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 3: Procedure of making joint

Picture of braided ReCF

Figure 4: Procedure of making braided ReCF series

Figure 5: Braided ReCF strand wound onto a bobbin

Table 1 shows an overview of the specimens used for the tensile tests. Braided ReCF strands with joints, braided ReCF strands without joint (no-joint ReCF), and virgin CF strands were prepared. Weight of each element is also shown in Table 1. The weight of braided ReCF strands was similar to that of no-joint ReCF strands. The weight of virgin CF strands was smallest. Although the virgin CF strands may have less number of fibers in the cross sectional area of the strand, the virgin CF strand was used to verify the variation of tensile strength comparing to that of other ReCF strands in this study. The length of each specimen was 500mm, and 100 specimens for each series were tested.

Table 1: Overview of each series

Series	Averaged weight (g)	Number of specimens for tensile tests
Braided ReCF	2.05	100
No-joint ReCF	2.12	100
Virgin CF	1.45	100

a) Braided ReCF series

b) No-joint ReCF series

c) Virgin CF series

Figure 6: Picture of each series

Figure 7 shows overview of each specimen. Iron pipes having the diameter of 16mm and length of 100mm were installed into both ends of the specimen. The gap between the pipe and the specimen was filled with epoxy resin. Test setup for tensile test is shown in Fig. 8. The testing machine grasped the pipe of the specimens. Loading rate was controlled at approximately 0.05 mm/s. The load was measured by using a load cell with a capacity of 10kN and an accuracy of 3N.

Figure 7: Tensile test specimens

Figure 8: Tensile test method

2.2 Results of tensile strength

Figure 9 shows the distribution of maximum loads from 100 specimens. In the braided ReCF series, the averaged maximum load was 0.99kN with a coefficient of variation of 0.4. In the no-joint ReCF series, the averaged maximum load was 1.97kN with a coefficient of variation of 0.14. In the virgin CF series, the averaged maximum load was 1.63kN with a coefficient of variation of 0.13. These results clearly indicate that the maximum load of the braided ReCF series was lowest, and the variability as indicated by the coefficient of variation was largest. It means that the connection by means of splicing and braiding should be improved.

Regardless of the difference between ReCF and virgin CF, the number of fibers in the strand is not constant, and it is currently difficult to measure the cross-sectional area of ReCF strands. The relationship between maximum load and weight are, therefore, investigated as shown in Fig. 10. The correlation coefficients were 0.54 for the braided ReCF series, 0.53 for the no-joint ReCF series, and 0.73 for the virgin CF series. It can be seen that all series have a positive correlation between maximum load and weight. It means that controlling the weight of each strand, which is equal to control the number of single fiber in ReCF strand, is important to reduce variation of maximum load in tension.

a) Braided ReCF series

b) No-joint ReCF series

c) Virgin CF series

Figure 9: Variability of maximum tensile load

a) Braided ReCF series

b) No-joint ReCF series

c) Virgin CF series

Figure 10: Relationship between maximum load and weight

Figure 11 shows distribution of maximum load normalized by its weight. The mean and coefficient of variation of the braided ReCF series were 475N/g and 0.22, while those of no-joint ReCF series were 965N/g and 0.12. , and those of the virgin material series were 1133N/g and 0.09. The variation of ReCF series regardless with and without joint was large comparing to that of virgin CF series.

Figure 11: Variation of maximum loads normalized by weight

2.3 Fracture mode of each series

Figure 12 shows the fracture mode of the braided ReCF series, no-joint ReCF series and virgin CF series. Although there was fracture at bulk part in the case of both the no-joint ReCF series and virgin CF series, the jointed part was fractured in the case of the braided ReCF series.

Figure 12: Fractured part of each series

3. STRENGTH IMPROVEMENT BY RESIN IMPREGNATION

3.1 Test specimens and resin impregnation method

In the previous chapter, fracture of jointed part was observed in the case of braided ReCF series. In order to improve the strength and to change failure behavior, epoxy resin was impregnated in this study. The braided ReCF series in the previous chapter was used. For comparison, single ReCF strand with joint (single ReCF strand) and no-joint ReCF series were also prepared for impregnation. Ten specimens for each series were prepared. Table 2 shows the averaged weight of the specimens (500mm in length) after impregnation.

Table 2: Weight of impregnated ReCF

Series	Total weight of ReCF (g)	Estimated weight of ReCF(g)	Estimated weight of epoxy(g)	$V_f(\%)$	Number of specimens
Braided ReCF	4.9	2.2	2.7	36	10
Single ReCF	4.7	0.7	4.0	11	10
No-joint ReCF	3.4	2.0	1.4	50	10

The resin used for the impregnation was epoxy resin (tensile strength in catalogue: 35 N/mm²). As shown in Figure 13, the ReCF was immersed in a tray filled with epoxy resin, and excess resin was removed by using a squeezer ($\phi 4\text{mm}$). The impregnated strands were kept for 48 hours in laboratory, and the specimen preparation for the tensile tests same as the previous chapter's manner was conducted.

Figure 13: Used impregnation method

Figure 14 shows the jointed part of the impregnated strands for each series. In general CFRP, the fiber volume content is reported as around 60% to 70% (Amijima, et al., 2013). In this study, the amount of resin in the prepared strands ranges from 11% to 50%, when densities of carbon fiber and epoxy resin are

assumed as 1.73 g/cm^3 and 1.20 g/cm^3 , respectively. It means that the impregnation was not enough, and voids may be existing inside of the strand. While the influence of resin content on strength needs to be further examined, the possibility of improving the joint strength of ReCF through resin impregnation has been demonstrated. Furthermore, it is desirable to reduce the resin content as much as possible from the perspectives of carbon neutrality and cost, so reducing the amount of resin will be a challenge in future work.

Figure 14: Specimens after impregnated

3.2 Result of tensile test

Figure 15 shows the tensile test results of the impregnated specimens. Note that, the tensile test was carried out according to the manner same as the previous chapter. The maximum load of the braided ReCF series was increased by 1.52kN, and that of the no-joint ReCF series was increased by 2.24 kN. The maximum load of the single ReCF series was 0.71 kN. The increase in maximum load indicates that the strength of the joint was improved by resin impregnation. Figure 16 shows examples of the fracture patterns of each series after the test. It was clarified that the bulk within the strand was fractured in all series, and the strength of the joints was improved by resin impregnation.

Figure 15: Maximum load obtained from impregnated specimen

a) Braided ReCF strand

b) Single ReCF strand

Figure 16: Impregnated specimens after tensile test

4. CONCLUSIONS

(1) The discretized ReCF obtained from heating method was connected by means of braiding technique. The strength of braided ReCF strand was not enough. In particular, variation of maximum load of braided ReCF strands was largest.

(2) Epoxy resin impregnation was effective to improve the strength of braided ReCF strand. In addition, it was possible to prevent the failure of jointed part of strands. The epoxy resin may be not perfectly injected into the voids of the strand, and further investigation are needed.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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